

INVESTIGATION OF DETECTIVE FICTION AND ITS TYPES

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Annotation. This article deals with the study of detective fiction which discusses specific features of detective genre. It gives information about this genre and its types with examples.

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Detective fiction is a subgenre of crime fiction and mystery fiction in which an investigator or a detective—whether professional, amateur or retired—investigates a crime, often murder. The detective genre began around the same time as speculative fiction and other genre fiction in the mid-nineteenth century and has remained extremely popular, particularly in novels. Some of the most famous heroes of detective fiction include C. Auguste Dupin, Sherlock Holmes, and Hercule Poirot. Juvenile stories featuring The Hardy Boys, Nancy Drew, and The Boxcar Children have also remained in print for several decades. The definition of a "good detective" is known, formulated by Van Dyne: A "good detective story" must have a clear plot with an almost complete absence of psychologism, since the narration itself resembles a cunningly woven crossword puzzle. According to this scheme, violence in a detective story should be minimal, and the story itself should have strict unity of style and general mood". Schematism and rationalism, which determined the logic of construction classic detective, were a product of scientific knowledge, which was characteristic of the nineteenth century. However, the scientific worldview, which contributed to the formation and development of technogenic civilization, by the beginning of the 20th century. loses its position. Rationalism began to be replaced by an irrational perception of reality. The onset of monopoly capital with its fierce competition, organized crime, corruption in public authorities, the First World War, which demonstrated to mankind the full range of technological possibilities, aimed at killing, called into question the possibilities of reason and science and caused a revision of the problem of the meaning of human existence, the place of man in the world. In such a society, the deductive method Sherlock Holmes was ill-suited for solving crimes. To replace the intellectual heroes of the classic detectives Ko nan Doyle, Agatha Christie, Chesterton and other detectives

of the "golden of the century, another hero came, a professional lone detective, physically strong and enduring, ready with the help of fists and weapons to seek justice in a society where the law, in his opinion, incapable of administering justice.

Over the years, detective fiction as a genre evolved and became an umbrella genre for numerous types of detective fiction, such as 'whodunits', police procedurals, serial killer thrillers, child(ren) detectives, cosy mysteries, and Sherlock Holmes narratives.

Whodunits or whodunnits are a type of detective fiction wherein the detective leads the investigation, collecting evidence, examining clues, and, most importantly, questioning witnesses. While the reader knows about the crime from the beginning, the detective uncovers a hidden narrative throughout the investigation that, in the end, helps the detective and the reader to identify the perpetrator of the crime.

For this reason, whodunits are said to have a double narrative, with one being the narrative that the reader is given from the beginning of the crime committed, and the other which is gradually uncovered as the perpetrator and their crime is revealed and explained. Detective fiction remains a widely-read genre today, and it has become increasingly sophisticated, evolving into long-standing bestseller series and prize-winning stand-alone novels. They provide the chance for justice to be served, and they engage with social commentary, often commenting on the state of society and law enforcement. Detective fiction invites audiences to solve crimes by piecing together clues of puzzles and offering them the thrill of decoding a mystery from their armchairs.

Cruelty and crime have become commonplace in American cities, which is reflected in the new type of detective stories with scenes of violence, which were absolutely not allowed in classic detective stories. In works that attracted the dangerous actions of a detective who tried to prove the guilt of the criminal, the element of solving was significantly weakened, and therefore there was no need to invent all sorts of cunning moves, as it was in the classic detective story. The image of a detective of a new type, the so-called "cool" (from English hardboiled, lit. "hard boiled") a guy named Reis Will yams, was first introduced in the story "Knights of the Mysterious Palm" by Carroll John Daly. It was from this work, published in 1923 in the popular American magazine Black Mask, that the victorious march of the "tough detective" began, which describes a real murder that returned "to the hands of those who commit it because of specific reasons, and not out of a desire to stock up on every case with a corpse, and this murder

is committed with anything, and not with a handmade duel pistol, curare poison or tropical fish," as was preferable in the classic detective story [1].

As a writer, K. Daley was in many ways inferior to other authors of the "hard detective", for example, Dashiell Hammett and Raymond Chandler, but his merit is that he, like Poe, was the founder of a new trend in crime literature. Theorists and defenders of the classic detective story, fearing for the purity of the genre, compiled a kind of instructions for writing a detective story, a kind of set of rules that were formulated by the Anglican pastor Ronald E. Knox in his work "The Ten Commandments of the detective novel" [2] and in close her, but containing a more extensive set of rules compiled by the American writer S.S. Van Dyne "Twenty Rules of Writing" detective novels" [3]. These rules consisting of the following provisions were quite rigid: "It is necessary to provide the reader with equal opportunities with the detective to unravel the mysteries, for which purpose it is necessary to clearly and accurately report all incriminating traces. With regard to the reader, only such tricks and deceit are allowed, which the criminal can apply to the detective. Love is forbidden. History should be a game of tag not between lovers, but between a detective and a criminal. Neither a detective nor any other professional investigator can be a criminal. Logical conclusions should lead to exposure. Random or unfounded confessions are not allowed. A detective cannot be absent from a detective who methodically searches for incriminating evidence, as a result of which he comes to the solution of the riddle. Mandatory crime in the detective - murder. In solving a given mystery, all supernatural forces and circumstances must be excluded.

Only one detective can operate in a story - the reader does not can compete with three or four members of the relay team at once. The perpetrator must be one of the more or less significant characters well known to the reader. An impermissibly cheap solution in which the perpetrator is one of the servants. Although the perpetrator may have an accomplice, the story is mostly should tell about the capture of one person.

Secret or criminal communities have no place in the detective story. The method of committing the murder and the methodology of the investigation must be reasonable and scientifically sound. To the savvy reader, the clue should be obvious. In a detective story there is no place for literature, descriptions painstakingly developed characters, coloring the situation by means of fiction.

The perpetrator can never be a professional villain. It is forbidden to attribute a secret to an accident or suicide. The motive for a crime is always private, it cannot be espionage action seasoned with some international intrigues, motives

of secret services. The author of detective stories should avoid all sorts of formulaic solutions, ideas. However, even during the lifetime of Van Dyne, these rules were subjected to serious criticism. In an article by a well-known American author of detective novels

Raymond Chandler "The Simple Art of Killing" [Chandler, 1990, with. 164–179], which was published in 1944, sets out and substantiates the claims of the "innovators" of the detective genre to the classic English detective story. Basically, he is criticized for implausibility, "pretentiousness and psychological unconvincing motivations that make the heroes of the detective paper dolls, whose actions are determined not by the internal logic of the character, but by the arbitrariness of the author, busy constructing another puzzle" [3].

The classic formula of the genre in the "hard" detective story - the investigation of a crime, culminating in a solution - was generally observed, although it was retouched, obeying the requirements of the new structure work, which is increasingly replenished with new elements. Method of mixing the old with the new American literary theorist Jonathan Culler has termed "the creation of a literary work" which is "at the same time an appeal to established formulas . . . and overcoming borders, going beyond them" [4].

In modern domestic literary criticism, there are ample opportunities for the transformation of the detective genre as a very mobile art system that can fit into others not originally associated with detective genres, including including in the works of "high" literature, enriching the traditional art space with new elements. The creation of hybrid works occurs with the help of new sociocultural iconic designs demanded by new heroes and events. New iconic designs, in turn, contribute to the assertion of new so-called "literary formulas" characteristic of a certain genre modification.

Literary formulas were the subject of the work of the American philologist John Cavelti "Adventure, mystery, love story: Formulaic Narratives as Art and Popular Culture", in which he introduces the concept of "formula, conventional" literature. "Formula" Cavelti called cultural stereotypes, traditional ways of describing, the general plot scheme inherent in works of popular literature that make the genre easy recognizable, which determines the success of these works, since only through the standardization of literature can the reader be I am sure in advance of the expected effect from reading the sold texts [Cavelti. The study of literary formulas]. At the same time, Cavelti defends formulaic literature from attacks on it as literature, carrying out an escapist a function that, in its essence,

makes life easier for a modern person, protecting him from the complexities of real life [5]

Stereotyping, clichédness is traditionally considered a property of second-rate, "lower" literature, while this property is inherent in one way or another in all literature as a whole, since defines an agreement or convention between reader and writer, in accordance with which the necessary contact between them is formed, which in principle is similar to the established order of behavior in society [Cavelti. The study of literary formulas]. Therefore, stereotyping, schematicity in literary works is not always means mediocrity. Observed in our time, the processes of erasing the boundaries between various genre modifications, between elitist and mass literature, which are based on different messages, are determined not so much by literary as by social processes. In the age of universal commercialization, "high" literature, following the example mass, also strives to achieve reader recognition not only among the elite, but also among the ordinary reader, which stimulates her to

the most attractive borrowings from popular literature, primarily from the works of the detective genre [6].

The effectiveness of the detective genre as a structure capable of attract the largest number of readers, owes its to the basic code: "a riddle – the process of solving it – a clue", which arouses the interest and intellectual tension of the reader. Thus, the detective becomes a breeding ground for emerging genres, which removes the sharpness of the distinction between mass and elite. However, from the point of view of the author of works devoted to detective genre, N.N. Volsky, numerous genre hybrids of recent years, united under the name "detective", do not have between nothing in common and do not at all testify to the transformation detective genre, but, in fact, about his death [Volsky. The case of the "detective without shores"] The detective story in the age of mass production faced an insoluble task: retaining the fundamental scheme of the classical detective story, adapting itself as a genre of popular literature in demand on the literary labor market. Big competition for the market of mass literature demanded from the writer a direct search for his reader, and the variety of literary requests led to the emergence of an incredible variety of "detective varieties" - "feminine", "spy", "historical", "ironic", etc. detectives, although, for example, "ironic detective" writes N. Volsky, is as far from a detective story as "socialist humanism" is from a humane attitude towards people" [Volsky. The case of the "detective without shores"], since it practically nullifies the main genre feature of the detective story is the

intellectual component of solving the crime. At best, the riddle is replaced some miserable similarities or absent altogether. These new formations are rather a mixture of various genres, for example, in the case of an ironic detective story, love and crime novels, while the detective story is a genre whose boundaries are rigidly outlined, and the goals were determined by Edgar Allan Poe and his followers [ibid.]. Thus, the existence of the detective genre in our time, found to be in conflict with the requirements of mass culture, has practically disappeared. In essence, Volsky's position is a continuation long-standing controversy between defenders of the purity of the genre of classical detective and "innovators" about the metamorphosis that took place with detective throughout the 20th century.

According to the majority of modern researchers, "modern detective, generating new literary modifications, loses the one-dimensionality of mass art" [Kuchumova, 2011, v. 1, with. 271-276]. In fact, there has been a complete devaluation of the detective genre and its absorption into mass literature, representing commercial, entertainment products.

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